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Estimation of tire forces, road grade, and road bank angle using tire model-less approaches and Fuzzy Logic.

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Abstract: This paper presents a modular observer structure to estimate the tire-road forces robustly, avoiding the use of any particular tire model, and using standard signals available in current passenger vehicles. The observer consists of a feedforward longitudinal force estimation block and a hybrid lateral force estimation module formed by an Extended Kalman Filter and a Static Neural Network Structure. Road grade and bank angle are estimated using sensor fusion, where a Fuzzy Logic controller combines the outputs from a Euler Kinematic model and a Recursive Least Squares block. The proposed observer is tested and verified using the simulation software *IPG CarMaker*® under realistic driving situations. Lastly, the feasibility of the longitudinal force block is proved with real-time experiments.

Keywords: Wheel-ground contact force estimation, bank angle estimation, road grade estimation, Fuzzy logic, Neural Networks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chassis stability and performance depend strongly on the forces generated at the tire contact patch. Thus, in order to develop robust chassis systems capable of enhancing these attributes, it is necessary to quantify these forces. As tire force transducers are still complex and expensive, virtual sensing is necessary to estimate the vehicle states using measurements from readily available sensors. Depending on the formulation employed in the construction of the state estimator, tire model-based and tire model-less approaches can be distinguished.

Concerning the first group, the *Magic Formula* Pacejka (2012) and the *Dugoff* tire models are often employed in the literature due to their suitability for real-time implementations. In Cordeiro et al. (2016) the *Dugoff* model is used to compute the tire longitudinal and lateral forces. The same formulation is adopted in Jiang et al. (2016); Doumiati et al. (2012, 2011, 2009). In Antonov et al. (2011) a simplified version of the *Magic Formula* is used to estimate the wheel-ground contact forces.

Tire model-less approaches are very attractive since a priori information regarding the tire-road interactions is not required to construct the observer. In Rajamani et al. (2012), a tire model-less approach based on the wheel dynamics is proposed to estimate the tire longitudinal forces. In Wilkin et al. (2006) a stochastic approach is adopted. The longitudinal and lateral forces are modeled as random walk variables and integrated into an Extended Kalman Filter *EKF* structure. In Baffet et al. (2009) a Sliding Mode Observer *SMO* is presented to estimate the

axle lateral forces and the front axle longitudinal force under the assumption of negligible rear axle longitudinal forces. The estimated forces are then used in an *EKF* where an adaptive cornering stiffness model is used to update a linear lateral tire force model.

A common assumption adopted in the literature is to consider the road as an even surface. Nevertheless, under realistic driving conditions, the performance of the state estimators is greatly affected by the road inclination angles Tseng (2001); Menhour et al. (2014); Grip et al. (2009). Thus, in order to minimize the state estimation error, it is necessary to consider the road orientation angles in the observer modelization. In Jiang et al. (2016, 2015) a steady-state method based on Recursive Least Squares *RLS* and readily available measurements is proposed to estimate the bank angle and road gradient. This approach is suitable for quasi-static conditions in which the approximation, $\dot{v}_y \approx 0$, holds. In Boada et al. (2016) a Dual Kalman Filter *DKF* approach is presented to estimate the road bank angle as well as relevant tire and chassis parameters. In Ryu and Christian Gerdes (2004), a disturbance observer is introduced to estimate the road bank angle and vehicle sideslip angle using a two-antenna GPS set up. In the latter works, the vehicle body slip angle is assumed to be a measurable signal, which might limit the applicability of these solutions in current passenger vehicles.

In this paper, a novel approach to estimate the road orientation angles and tire planar forces is proposed. The contribution of this article lies fundamentally in the sensor fusion approach proposed to estimate accurately the road grade and bank angle during transient and steady-state

situations. The estimated road orientation angles are included in the formulation of the tire force estimators, in order to make these robust under realistic driving situations (e.g. non-flat surfaces). In addition, this is carried out using tire model-less approaches and readily available measurements, which facilitates the implementation of the observers.

The complete observer structure is presented in Section 2. The road angle observer and the theoretical background necessary for its formulation are detailed in Section 3. The longitudinal and lateral force estimation blocks are described in Sections 4 and 5 respectively. Simulation results obtained in *IPG CarMaker*® as well as experimental tests are discussed in Section 6. Finally, relevant conclusions and further research steps are presented in Section 7.

2. OBSERVER STRUCTURE

The observer structure is shown in Fig. 1. A modular structure is proposed with the aim to lessen the tuning effort of the state estimator. This is formed by a Longitudinal force block, an *EKF*, a Static Neural Networks block *NN*, and a Fuzzy road angle estimator *FUZZY*. The inputs and outputs used by each block are presented in Table 1. As portrayed in the diagram, the estimation of the road inclination angles is carried out separately from the estimation of the tire forces. The chassis orientation angles with respect to the inertial reference frame ($\hat{\theta}_{FUZ}, \hat{\phi}_{FUZ}$) are computed in the *Fuzzy* block using a sensor fusion approach. The road grade (θ_r) and bank angle (ϕ_r) are calculated after compensating the latter angles with the body roll (ϕ_b) and body pitch (θ_b), inferred from the vehicle accelerations using a transfer function approach. The variables p, q and r denote the body-axis angular rates in the x, y and z directions respectively.

The axle longitudinal forces are estimated from the vehicle longitudinal acceleration. The road grade and absolute pitch angles estimated in the upper-level block are introduced in the longitudinal force module to compensate the gravitational effects on the measured acceleration (a_{xm}). The estimated longitudinal forces and the measured average wheel speed (ω_{avg}), yaw rate (r) and steering angle (δ) are passed through the *EKF* block.

Fig. 1. Observer diagram

Table 1. Inputs and outputs of the observer.

	F_x	EKF	NN	Fuzzy
Inputs	a_{xm}	F_x, δ	a_{xm}, α	$a_{xm}, a_{ym}, \dot{a}_{ym}, r$
	$\hat{\theta}_{FUZ}, \theta_r$	r, ω_{avg}		$p, q, \omega_{avg}, \dot{\omega}_{avg}$
Outputs	F_x	F_y, r, v_x, v_y	F_{y0}, C	$\hat{\theta}_{FUZ}, \hat{\phi}_{FUZ}$

The vehicle planar dynamics are contained in the *EKF* block. The road inclination angles have been incorporated into the vehicle planar dynamics equations (6-7) in order to have an accurate estimation of the vehicle states (v_x, v_y, r) during non-flat road segments. The vehicle axle slips (α) computed by the *EKF* are then used in the *NN* block where the uncertain tire parameters (F_{y0}, C) are estimated. The measured longitudinal acceleration is introduced in the *NN* block to take into account the lateral force reduction due to combined solicitations.

2.1 Extended Kalman Filter

The state space formulation of a nonlinear system is given by expressions (1 - 2).

$$X_k = f_k(X_{k-1}, U_k) \quad (1)$$

$$Y_k = h(X_k) \quad (2)$$

where the *EKF* state (X_k), input (U_k) and measurement (Y_k) vectors are expressed by (3 - 5),

$$U_k = (\delta_k, F_{xf,k}, F_{xr,k}) \quad (3)$$

$$X_k = (r_k, v_{x,k}, v_{y,k}) \quad (4)$$

$$Y_k = (r_k, \omega_{avg,k}) \quad (5)$$

and the state evolution vector $f(\cdot)$ is constructed from equations (6 - 8).

$$m(\dot{v}_x - v_y r) = F_{xf} \cos(\delta) - F_{yf} \sin(\delta) + F_{xr} + mg \sin(\theta_r) \quad (6)$$

$$m(\dot{v}_y + v_x r) = F_{yf} \cos(\delta) + F_{xf} \sin(\delta) + F_{yr} - mg \cos(\theta_r) \sin(\phi_r) \quad (7)$$

$$I_\psi \dot{r} = (F_{yf} \cos(\delta) + F_{xf} \sin(\delta)) l_f - F_{yr} l_r \quad (8)$$

The complete formulation of the filter is omitted in this paper due to space limitations. For additional details regarding the filter construction and observability analysis Doumiati et al. (2012, 2009) can be consulted.

3. ROAD ANGLE OBSERVER

Fig. 2. Diagram of the absolute roll and pitch orientation angles observer.

As depicted in Fig. 2, the structure of the *FUZZY* observer is formed by an *Euler-Kinematic* and a *RLS* model. The signal fusion of these blocks is accomplished by a Fuzzy Logic Controller. The idea behind this concept is to use

the Kinematic model in transient dynamic situations and switch into the RLS block when the dynamic excitation is low and the Kinematic model is prone to drift (steady-state driving). A Fuzzy Logic controller has been chosen to carry out the sensor fusion due to its implementation ease and the possibility of including heuristic control in the form of *if-then* rules, see Sivanandam et al. (2007) for more information.

3.1 Kinematic model

Fig. 3. Scheme of the Inertial frame, road-fixed frame and body-fixed frame

From Figure 3, the following coordinate frames could be defined: I_0 , (Inertial reference frame), I_b , (Body-fixed frame) and I_r (road-fixed frame). In this paper, the ISO rotation convention (yaw- ψ pitch- θ roll- ϕ) is used. Assuming that an Inertial Measurement Unit *IMU*, can be placed exactly at the center of gravity location, the Euler angles of the chassis body with respect to the inertial frame (θ, ϕ) can be obtained by direct integration of the expression (9).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{bmatrix}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sin \phi \tan \phi & \cos \phi \tan \phi \\ 0 & \cos \phi & -\sin \phi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Once the chassis body angles are computed, the earth gravity vector (G) can be expressed in the body-fixed frame (g_b) using expression (10), where $R_I^b(\phi, \theta)$ is the rotation matrix defined in (11).

$$g_b = [g_{bx} \ g_{by} \ g_{bz}]^T = R_I^b(\phi, \theta)G \quad (10)$$

$$R_I^b = R(\phi)R(\theta)R(\psi) \quad (11)$$

Finally, as the planar dynamics equations are formulated in the road-fixed frame, it is necessary to translate the gravity components from I_b to I_r . A rigorous approach requires the definition of the inverse rotation matrix $R_b^r(\phi_b, \theta_b)$, given by (12).

$$R_b^r(\phi_b, \theta_b) = IR(-\theta_b)R(-\phi_b) \quad (12)$$

Where the inertial reference frame I_0 is considered to rotate parallel to the z -axis of the body and road-fixed

frames ($R(\psi) = I$). The gravity components are translated to the road-fixed frame using the expression (13).

$$g_r = R_b^r g_b = R_b^r R_I^b G \quad (13)$$

Fortunately, the computation of the inverse rotation matrix can be avoided if decoupled suspension pitch (θ_b) and roll (ϕ_b) angles are assumed. Then, the road angles can be obtained by expressions (14-15), where the subindex b denotes the rotations of the body-fixed frame with respect to the road-fixed frame. Simulations showed negligible errors when using the simplified calculation.

$$\phi_r \approx \phi - \phi_b \quad (14)$$

$$\theta_r \approx \theta - \theta_b \quad (15)$$

3.2 Recursive Least Squares

From the IMU accelerations (a_{ym}, a_{xm}), and considering a small angle approximation, the body orientation angles can be obtained from expressions (16 - 17) using a linear recursive identification algorithm, *RLS*, Jiang et al. (2015). A forgetting factor is introduced to reduce the weight of older error samples.

$$\dot{w}_{avg} R_{nom} - a_{xm} = g\theta \quad (16)$$

$$a_{ym} - r w_{avg} R_{nom} = g\phi \quad (17)$$

Eq. (17) is formulated assuming that the derivative of the lateral velocity is null ($\dot{v}_y \approx 0$). Additionally, (16) approximates the chassis longitudinal acceleration by the derivative of the average rear wheel speed (\dot{w}_{avg}). Due to the wheel speed fluctuations during braking-acceleration events, and the sideslip rate component during the transient lateral dynamics, these expressions are only suitable to estimate the chassis orientation angles during steady-state situations.

3.3 Suspension transfer functions

A transfer function approach is used to estimate the chassis roll and pitch angles from the IMU acceleration measurements, eq. (18). The transfer function coefficients of the structure depicted in Fig. 1 are obtained using the *Matlab*® System Identification Toolbox after executing several *Frequency Response* and *Pitch Evolution* tests in *IPG-CarMaker*®.

$$\phi_b(s)(s^2 I_\phi + s C_\phi + K_\phi) = a_{ym}(s)m(h_{CoG} - h_{CIR}) \quad (18)$$

3.4 Fuzzy logic integration

Firstly, the kinematic model output is reset each time steady-state conditions are met. New initial conditions (provided by the *RLS*) are imposed during each reset. This prevents the kinematic model from drifting during long periods in standstill or low dynamic excitation. As shown in the algorithm, the wheel acceleration (\dot{w}_{avg}), lateral jerk (\dot{a}_{ym}), and body rates (p, q, r) contained in the vector Z have to keep during a Δt within the dynamic threshold

Z^* , (steady-state situation). During this time, an average of the RLS values θ_{RLS} , ϕ_{RLS} is taken, and imposed when the $RESET$ flag is triggered. Finally, if during the Δt period the states Z leave the steady-state condition, the system is initialized.

Fig. 4. Membership functions of fuzzy input variables ($\dot{a}_{ym}, \dot{w}_{avg}$), and fuzzy outputs (k_1, k_2).

The signal fusion is performed using expression (19), where the gains k_1, k_2 are set by a Fuzzy Logic Controller. When the Fuzzy controller detects sudden changes in the lateral jerk (\dot{a}_{ym}) or the rear wheel acceleration (\dot{w}_{avg}) the RLS gain (k_1) is reduced to minimize the errors derived from the RLS module. On the other hand, when the value of the previous states is reduced (steady-state) the kinematic gain (k_2) is lowered to avoid error from the IMU rate bias.

$$\hat{y} = \frac{k_1 y_{RLS} + k_2 y_{kin}}{k_1 + k_2} \quad (19)$$

The fuzzy variables, as well as their respective Membership Functions, are showed in Fig. 4. An *if-then* table is constructed, Table. 2 and the Mandani's Fuzzy Inference Method is followed.

Algorithm 1 Kinematic Reset Algorithm

INPUT: $Z, t, \theta_{RLS}, \phi_{RLS}, SS_{FLAG}, RESET$

OUTPUT: $SS_{FLAG}, \theta_0, \phi_0$

```

1:  $RESET = 0$ 
2: if  $|Z| < Z^*$  then
3:   if  $SS_{FLAG} == 0$  then
4:      $SS_{FLAG} = 1$ 
5:      $t_{ss} = t$ 
6:   else
7:     if  $t_{ss} < t < (t_{ss} + \Delta t)$  then
8:        $\theta_0 = \bar{\theta}_{RLS}$ 
9:        $\phi_0 = \bar{\phi}_{RLS}$ 
10:    else
11:       $RESET = 1$ 
12:    end if
13:  end if
14: else
15:    $t_{ss} = inf$ 
16:    $SS_{FLAG} = 0$ 
17:    $\theta_0 = 0$ 
18:    $\phi_0 = 0$ 
19: end if

```

Finally, the centroid method is adopted for the defuzzification of the crisp outputs, Sivanandam et al. (2007).

4. LONGITUDINAL FORCE ESTIMATION

In this section, the force estimator is developed from the bicycle model introduced in equation (6). As shown in Figure 1, the output of this algorithm is used as an input to the Extended Kalman Filter. Several approaches have been studied to estimate the longitudinal forces, from tire model-based relying on the tire longitudinal slip computation (λ) to experimental analysis of the tire longitudinal deformation. These methods are costly and not easily applicable in a passenger vehicle, therefore, here is proposed a simplified estimation model based on the vehicle longitudinal acceleration a_x , defined as,

$$F_{xf} = c_1 \cdot (a_x + g \cdot \sin(\theta_r)) + c_2 \quad (20)$$

$$F_{xr} = c_3 \cdot (a_x + g \cdot \sin(\theta_r)) + c_4 \quad (21)$$

where $a_x = \dot{v}_x - v_y \cdot r$, from equation (6).

In this model, the coefficients c_1, c_3 depend strongly on the wheel traction and brake distribution of the vehicle and are affected by changes in vehicle's mass distribution. Coefficients c_2 and c_4 are included to compensate the effects derived from rolling resistance and drag forces. These coefficients are defined while accelerating as

$$c_1 = m_v; \quad c_3 = 0;$$

and during braking

$$c_1 = \gamma_1 \cdot m_v; \quad c_3 = \gamma_2 \cdot m_v;$$

with γ_1 and γ_2 being the braking distribution between front and rear wheels. These values are defined in the vehicle design stage and satisfy $\gamma_1 + \gamma_2 = 1$.

The braking force is distributed between the front and rear wheels such that the longitudinal force acts on all wheels. Under acceleration, only the driven wheels produce longitudinal forces, while in the rear wheels is produced a just a reacting force that opposes the movement. In the case of an all-wheel-drive vehicle, the total driving force is divided according to the driving force distribution of the vehicles powertrain. For simplicity, aerodynamic drag is not considered in this work, but additional coefficients dependent on v_x^2 can be easily incorporated into the current model structure. Finally, the road grade is obtained from (15), and a_x is calculated by compensating the bias of the measured acceleration a_{xm} with the estimated pitch angle $\hat{\theta}$.

5. LATERAL FORCE ESTIMATION

The generation of a precise tire model for the estimation of the lateral forces is not trivial and involves extensive testing. In addition, the outputs from the model might be subjected to an important source of uncertainties derived from other vehicle subsystems (e.g. elasto-kinematics from

Table 2. Rule table of the Fuzzy roll controller

	Jerk	L	ML	H	VH
Wheel acc.	BRK	ML L	L H	L H	VL VH
	CD	H L	MH MH	MH H	L VH
	ACC	MH L	ML MH	ML H	VL VH

the suspension system). In order to avoid these shortcomings, an approach that uses vehicle's high-level data generated from open loop maneuvers is proposed.

A first order linearization of the nonlinear force-slip function is proposed to model the tire lateral forces (22 - 23). For simplicity, a static force-slip relationship is assumed.

$$F_y \approx F_{y0} + \frac{\partial F_y}{\partial \alpha} \Delta \alpha \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial F_y}{\partial \alpha} \approx \frac{F_{y,\alpha_0+\Delta\alpha_t} - F_{y,\alpha_0-\Delta\alpha_t}}{2\Delta\alpha_t} \quad (23)$$

The equilibrium lateral force (F_{y0}) and the first order derivative ($\frac{\partial F_{y0}}{\partial \alpha}$) are obtained from a Static Neural Network block. The term $\Delta\alpha_t$ denotes the slip-step used to compute the first order derivative of the lateral force using finite differences. Different step sizes were evaluated and a good match between the real and approximated cornering stiffness was seen for a value of 0.02 radians.

The suitability of this methodology has been proved in previous works Acosta and Kanarachos (2017), where this approach is validated using a high-fidelity vehicle model in *IPG CarMaker* and a state-of-the-art *6.1 MF* tire model. Moreover, sensitivity analyses to evaluate the robustness of this solution against uncertainties in the tire pressure or the tire size were presented.

5.1 Neural Networks

Static Neural Networks are used to estimate the tire states due to their remarkable fitting capabilities, Pasterkamp and Pacejka (1997), Melzi and Sabbioni (2011). In order to train the *NN* structure, a training dataset was generated using the Simulation Package *IPG-CarMaker*[®]. Aggressive step-steer maneuvers, ISO (2011), covering different longitudinal acceleration levels (*braking in a turn, power on*) were selected due to their repeatability, easiness of execution and capability to excite a wide range of the tire non-linear region.

The *Matlab*[®]Neural Networks toolbox was used to construct and train the *NN* block. The Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation algorithm was selected to train the structure and the training dataset was divided into a 70/15/15% proportion to set the neurons' weight. The process was repeated several times in order to study the stability of the structure, Belic (2012). Finally, a 10-Neurons Hidden-layer structure was chosen after showing the best performance, (Acosta and Kanarachos, 2017).

6. RESULTS

6.1 Simulation results - Nordschleife

The virtual tire force sensors were implemented in *Simulink*[®], *IPG-CarMaker*[®]. The first order equations were discretized using a first order Euler expansion ($1 + AT_s$) and a sample time $T_s = 1ms$. In order to evaluate the performance of the *EKF*, white gaussian noise was added to the measurement inputs and the signals were sampled at a frequency of $100Hz$, Table. 3, Racelogic (2016). The *EKF* plant (Q) and measurement (R) noise covariance matrices

were tuned accordingly. The IMU gyro bias stability was modeled as a random variable, Woodman (2007).

Table 3. Added white gaussian noise

σ_{a_x} [m/s ²]	σ_{a_y} [m/s ²]	σ_{gyro} [rad/s]	$\sigma_{gyrobias}$ [rad/s]	σ_w [m/s]
0.01	0.01	0.002	1.2e-4	0.03

An IMU unit was placed in the Centre of Gravity of the *IPG - DemoCar*. Wheel speed and lateral acceleration signals were low-passed filtered to minimize the noise caused by the numerical differentiation. In order

Fig. 5. Simulations results obtained in *IPG-CarMaker*[®]

to test the tire-force observer under high-demanding environments, simulations were carried out on Nordschleife Racetrack (first 5km). The driver thresholds were adjusted to ($6m/s^2$) to reproduce a sporty driving style. The simulation results are depicted on Figure 5.

Fig. 6. Estimated F_x responses compared to the real values computed by simulation.

In Figure 6 the longitudinal force estimates are displayed. It is worth mentioning that despite using simplified algorithms, the performance of the estimator is remarkable. Concerning the rear longitudinal forces, the improvement is considerable with respect to other approaches commonly adopted in the literature, where null rear longitudinal forces are assumed for a front wheel drive vehicle $F_{xr} = 0$.

Fig. 7. Estimated F_y responses compared to the real values computed by simulation.

Simulated and estimated axle lateral forces are depicted in Fig. 7. As can be seen, by including the estimated road angles (*with comp.* curve) on the planar dynamics equations (6 - 8), the lateral force error is reduced to less than 5%, Table 4. The (*w/o comp.*) curve has been added to show the error derived from the horizontal surface assumption.

Table 4. Standard deviation of normalized errors. Lateral forces, road grade and bank angle.

	$e_{F_{yf}}$ [%]	$e_{F_{yr}}$ [%]		e_{θ_r} [%]	e_{ϕ_r} [%]
W/o c.	11.18	8.91	Fuzzy est.	9.63	8.18
W c.	4.33	4.31	RLS est.	36.06	23.01

Fig. 8. Plot of Fuzzy, RLS and real road grade and bank angles.

Finally, Fig. 8 exhibits the results obtained with the *FUZZY* road angle observer. As can be noticed, the observer "filters" the *RLS* signals in high-dynamic situations, thus reducing the road inclination error below the 10% band, Table. 4.

6.2 Real Time Experiments

The testbed at HEUDIASYC UMR 7253 CNRS, Compiègne, France, and the main sensors and software modules which compose it are shown in Figure 9. This vehicle is instrumented with four wheel force transducers which measure the forces and torques for the x , y and z axis. It is also instrumented with an Inertial Measurement Unit

from which it is possible to obtain the vehicle accelerations (a_{xm} , a_{ym} , a_{zm}) and angular rates (r , q , p). To validate

Fig. 9. Peugeot 308sw experimental testbed developed at Université de Technologie de Compiègne

the proposed longitudinal force estimator, the mission depicted in Figure 10 is carried out. A top speed of 150 km/hr is reached while performing aggressive maneuvers. An experimental fine-tuning was carried out with the coefficients c_1 , c_2 , c_3 and c_4 in order to capture the variations in mass distribution, brake system, etc. between the simulation and the experimental vehicle. In Figure

Fig. 10. Mission performed to validate the longitudinal force estimator.

Fig. 11. Estimated F_x responses compared to the measurements obtained from the Kistler Roadyn sensor

11 the experimental results are shown after performing the test depicted in Fig. 10. As occurred during the simulation validation (see Fig. 6), the front longitudinal force estimator exhibits a good behavior and an accurate response. Estimated forces (F_x est) are displayed with a solid red line, while the Roadyn transducer responses are depicted in blue dashed trace. On the other hand, some inaccuracies are observed in the rear longitudinal force responses. In this case, the force values are low, and the signal-to-noise ratio is reduced, being factors such as the uncertainty associated with the rolling resistance more noticeable.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a robust virtual tire force sensor for the estimation of the wheel-ground contact forces under aggressive driving on non-flat road segments has been proposed. Moreover, the estimation of these forces is carried out using standard signals available in current vehicles (wheel speed, accelerations, yaw rate), thus avoiding the installation of additional instrumentation. A hybrid road grade and road bank angle observer has been designed and integrated into the estimator structure with the aim to minimize the estimation error during inclined road segments. Simulations in *IPG CarMaker*® have been performed to evaluate the estimator robustness under realistic driving conditions. Overall, the performance exhibited by the virtual sensors is remarkable, and the road angle compensation minimizes considerably the error associated with the wheel-ground force estimation. Finally, experimental tests have been performed to validate the longitudinal force estimator. Experimental validation of the whole observer structure will be pursued during the next research steps.

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